

ALEVIA: A Two-Stage Deep Learning Pipeline for Multi-Label Morphological Deformity Classification in Juvenile *Sparus aurata* and *Dicentrarchus labrax*

Javier Álvarez Osuna

Feeding Systems S.L. – FishFarmFeeder
javier.osuna@fishfarmfeeder.com

Francisco Fernández Vilor

Feeding Systems S.L. – FishFarmFeeder
paco.vilor@fishfarmfeeder.com

Abstract—Intensive mariculture of juvenile gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) and European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) depends on early morphological screening to contain deformity rates below market thresholds ($< 3\%$), yet this process still relies almost exclusively on manual inspection. We present ALEVIA, a two-stage deep learning pipeline that processes a single lateral fish image to (i) detect, segment, and identify the species using YOLOv11, then (ii) classify the segmented crop for up to seven concurrent phenotypic deformity classes per species using a ResNet-34 multi-label classifier augmented with Grad-CAM++ for decision explainability. Multi-label formulation naturally handles co-occurring deformities and avoids the combinatorial proliferation of independent binary classifiers. Trained on 3,325 high-resolution laboratory images, Stage 1 achieves near-perfect segmentation performance ($mAP_{50-95} = 0.995$ on both species). Stage 2 reaches a weighted macro F1-score of 0.849 for *S. aurata* and 0.721 for *D. labrax* on held-out test sets. The complete pipeline exceeds the 2 img/s throughput requirement on commodity CPU hardware (median latency 315 ms/image, ≈ 3.17 img/s). Grad-CAM++ visualisations confirm anatomically consistent activation patterns, providing an interpretable audit trail for domain-expert validation. The system constitutes the inference module of the ALEVIA Gaia-X-compliant federated data space for precision aquaculture.

Index Terms—aquaculture, morphological deformity, multi-label classification, instance segmentation, YOLOv11, ResNet-34, Grad-CAM, precision fish farming

I. INTRODUCTION

Intensive production of juvenile *Sparus aurata* (gilthead sea bream) and *Dicentrarchus labrax* (European sea bass) is a strategic segment of Mediterranean mariculture, ranking among the most economically significant operations in European aquaculture [1]. Skeletal and morphofunctional deformities in early larvae and juveniles—vertebral anomalies, opercular defects, craniofacial malformations—arise from nutritional, environmental, and mechanical factors during development and have been systematically documented in farmed European marine fish populations [2], [3]. Their presence reduces specific growth rate, worsens feed conversion ratios, increases intra-batch variability, and inflates the fraction of rejected individuals at harvest [4]–[6].

In commercial hatcheries and nurseries, deformed individuals are routinely culled to maintain deformity rates below the market threshold. This process is almost exclusively manual, dependent on operator expertise, and subject to significant inter-

observer variability [7], [8]. At production volumes reaching hundreds of thousands of juveniles per campaign, individualised visual inspection is not systematically feasible, resulting in partial and heterogeneous sorting. Beyond the immediate sorting inefficiency, individuals with subclinical morphological alterations that escape detection continue through the production cycle, subsequently exhibiting lower growth rate, higher feed conversion indices, and greater susceptibility to stress and disease [5].

The transition towards automated phenotypic screening via computer vision and machine learning aligns with the *Precision Fish Farming* paradigm [1], which advocates data-driven decision-making to optimise biological performance and environmental sustainability. However, specific applications of these principles to early phenotype assessment in sea bream and sea bass juveniles—with the goal of productive viability prediction—remain at an incipient stage and lack commercially validated solutions.

This paper presents ALEVIA, a two-stage pipeline that addresses this gap. Given a single lateral image of a fish specimen, the system: (i) detects and segments the fish and identifies its species using YOLOv11 [9]; (ii) classifies the segmented crop for the presence of up to seven deformity classes per species using a ResNet-34 [10] multi-label classifier, augmented with Grad-CAM++ for decision explainability [11]. The multi-label formulation is central to the design: a single specimen may simultaneously exhibit multiple morphological anomalies, and encoding this as a binary vector is both semantically accurate and computationally efficient compared to deploying an ensemble of independent binary classifiers.

The main contributions of this work are:

- A validated two-stage instance segmentation + multi-label classification pipeline for fish larval deformity inspection, achieving state-of-the-art performance on a real-world aquaculture dataset.
- Empirical demonstration of computational feasibility for real-time deployment (> 2 img/s) on commodity CPU hardware without dedicated GPU acceleration.
- Qualitative validation via Grad-CAM++ that the learned representations attend to anatomically meaningful regions, producing an interpretable audit trail for expert validation.
- Integration of the inference pipeline into the ALEVIA

Gaia-X-compliant federated data space for precision aquaculture, enabling privacy-preserving cross-facility corpus accumulation.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. CNN-Based Visual Recognition

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) exploit local receptive fields, weight sharing, and spatial subsampling to model the spatial structure of images at a fraction of the parameter count of fully-connected networks [12]. Formally, a convolutional layer computes:

$$Y_{k,i,j} = \sum_{c=1}^{C_{in}} \sum_{u=1}^f \sum_{v=1}^f W_{k,c,u,v} \cdot X_{c,i+u-1,j+v-1} + b_k \quad (1)$$

where f is the filter spatial size and b_k a learnable bias. Early filters respond to oriented edges and colour blobs; deeper filters detect textures and object parts [13]. Two architectural families are particularly relevant to this work: ResNet for accuracy-critical classification and YOLO for real-time detection.

B. YOLO: Unified Real-Time Object Detection

YOLO [14] reformulates object detection as a single regression problem over an $S \times S$ grid, where each cell predicts B bounding boxes with confidence scores and C class probabilities, resolved in a single forward pass. YOLO11 [9], the version used here, extends this to instance segmentation via a mask head and incorporates improved attention mechanisms, achieving >45 FPS on standard GPU hardware.

C. ResNet: Deep Residual Learning

He *et al.* [10] introduced shortcut connections to address the *degradation problem* in deep networks, reformulating each block to learn the residual:

$$F(\mathbf{x}) = H(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{x}, \quad \text{output} = F(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{x} \quad (2)$$

This preserves gradient flow across hundreds of layers with no additional parameters. ResNet-34, employed in this work, provides a favourable accuracy/latency trade-off and is available with ImageNet-pretrained weights in all major deep learning frameworks, enabling efficient transfer learning on domain-specific datasets of limited size.

D. Grad-CAM: Visual Explanations for CNNs

Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping [11] produces a coarse localisation map highlighting the image regions most influential for a given prediction. For class c , the importance weight of channel k in the last convolutional layer is:

$$\alpha_k^c = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\partial y^c}{\partial A_{ij}^k} \quad (3)$$

and the final heat map is:

$$L_{\text{Grad-CAM}}^c = \text{ReLU} \left(\sum_k \alpha_k^c A^k \right) \quad (4)$$

The ReLU retains only channels that positively influence class c . Grad-CAM++ extends the formulation by weighting individual spatial positions of the gradient, yielding sharper localisations.

E. DL for Fish Disease and Deformity Detection

Computer vision has been applied to aquaculture monitoring across a broad range of tasks—species classification, biomass estimation, behaviour analysis, and disease screening—as surveyed by Li and Du [15]. Within disease detection, CNN-based approaches have demonstrated consistent advantages over manual inspection: Ahmed *et al.* [8] reported classifiers operating on still images with accuracy exceeding 90%, and Cai *et al.* [16] proposed a NAM-YOLOv7 hybrid that achieves near-perfect detection of Spring Viremia of Carp in pond footage (precision 99.75%, recall 99.31%). These works, however, address chromatic or textural skin lesions detectable in underwater video, not structural skeletal deformities assessed from individual dorso-lateral still images under controlled conditions.

The closest domain to ALEVIA is the automated detection of external and skeletal anomalies in farmed marine fish. Kumar *et al.* [17] survey bioimage analysis methods for deformity detection in seabream, zebrafish, and medaka, and identify two open problems that ALEVIA directly addresses: the scarcity of multi-class annotated datasets and the absence of simultaneous multi-label deformity predictors. A concurrent work [18] applies YOLOv12s to detect pectoral and caudal fin deformities and opercular lesions in underwater stereovision imagery of *D. labrax* and *S. aurata* (mAP up to 0.91). ALEVIA differs from this work in three key respects: (i) it operates on high-resolution controlled still images rather than underwater video; (ii) it jointly identifies seven deformity classes per species using a multi-label formulation; and (iii) it integrates species identification as a preceding pipeline stage. To our knowledge, no prior published system combines instance segmentation, species identification, and multi-label deformity classification across both target species in a single end-to-end inference pipeline.

F. Multi-Label Classification in Bioimaging

Multi-label classification—where each image may simultaneously carry multiple ground-truth labels—is established in medical image analysis. Wang *et al.* [19] demonstrated with ChestX-ray14 (112,120 chest radiographs, 14 co-occurring pathologies) that a multi-label CNN trained with weighted binary cross-entropy consistently outperforms independent binary classifiers by capturing inter-label co-occurrence patterns through shared convolutional representations. Baltruschat *et al.* [20] confirmed this in a systematic 5-fold evaluation comparing ResNet and DenseNet on the same dataset, and identified the weighted macro F1-score as the appropriate reference metric under severe class imbalance—a finding directly applicable to aquaculture deformity classification, where healthy specimens typically dominate the corpus. In both cases, a single multi-label model trained end-to-end is preferable to a parallel ensemble of binary classifiers, not only for computational efficiency but because shared feature extraction provides implicit regularisation for underrepresented classes. ALEVIA adopts this paradigm, training one ResNet-34 multi-label model per species rather than N_c independent binary models per species.

Fig. 1. Per-class image counts for *S. aurata* (left) and *D. labrax* (right). Green bars indicate the healthy class.

Fig. 2. Representative dataset images: individual fish centred on a white background with a reference ruler (lateral projection).

III. DATASET

The dataset comprises 3,325 high-resolution images ($4,592 \times 3,448$ px) of individual fish specimens, each centred on a white background with a reference ruler. Images are organised hierarchically by species and deformity type, enabling both taxonomic and pathological filtering. Of the total, 2,205 images correspond to *S. aurata* and 1,120 to *D. labrax*. Class imbalance is pronounced, particularly for *D. labrax*, where 65.98% of specimens present no deformity. Fig. 1 shows per-class sample counts; Fig. 2 shows representative images.

S. aurata is annotated for seven deformity classes: mouth, caudal, vertebral fusion, lordosis, snout, operculum, and SBS (Short Body Syndrome). *D. labrax* is annotated for three: vertebral fusion, lordosis, and SBS. Multi-label annotation allows simultaneous presence of multiple deformities in the same specimen, which is clinically documented in intensive aquaculture populations [2].

IV. METHOD

The ALEVIA pipeline processes a single lateral RGB image through two sequential stages (Figs. 3–4). Stage 1 detects and segments the fish while identifying its species. Stage 2 classifies the segmented crop for the presence of each deformity class and produces a Grad-CAM++ explainability map.

A. Stage 1: Detection, Segmentation, and Species Identification

1) *Chromatic Preprocessing*: The input tensor $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3448 \times 4592}$ is first corrected for chromatic bias via the Gray

Algorithm 1 Gray World White Balance

Require: RGB image $I \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3}$
Ensure: White-balanced image I_{wb}

- 1: $I_f \leftarrow \text{TOFLOAT}(I)$
- 2: **for** $c \in \{R, G, B\}$ **do**
- 3: $\mu_c \leftarrow \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{i,j} I_f^{(c)}(i, j)$
- 4: **end for**
- 5: $\mu_{\text{grey}} \leftarrow (\mu_R + \mu_G + \mu_B)/3$
- 6: **for** $c \in \{R, G, B\}$ **do**
- 7: $\alpha_c \leftarrow \mu_{\text{grey}}/\mu_c$ **if** $\mu_c > 0$ **else** 1
- 8: $I_f^{(c)} \leftarrow \alpha_c \cdot I_f^{(c)}$
- 9: **end for**
- 10: **return** $\text{TOUINT8}(\text{CLIP}(I_f, 0, 255))$

Algorithm 2 Fish Detection, Segmentation, and Species ID

Require: Image I_{in} , model M , confidence τ , dilation kernel size k
Ensure: Segmented crop $I_{\text{crop}}^{\text{seg}}$, species s

- 1: $I \leftarrow \text{READIMAGE}(I_{in})$
- 2: $I_{\text{pre}} \leftarrow \text{GRAYWORLDWB}(\text{BGR2RGB}(I))$
- 3: $R \leftarrow \text{INFERYOLO}(M, I_{\text{pre}}, \tau)$
- 4: **if** $R = \emptyset$ **or** $\text{BOXES}(R) = \emptyset$ **then**
- 5: **raise** NoDetectionError
- 6: **end if**
- 7: $b \leftarrow \text{FIRSTBOX}(R)$; $s \leftarrow \text{CLASSNAME}(R, b)$
- 8: $Q \leftarrow \text{FIRSTMASKCONTOUR}(R)$
- 9: $B \leftarrow \text{ZEROMASK}(H, W)$; $B \leftarrow \text{FILLCONTOUR}(B, Q)$
- 10: $B \leftarrow \text{DILATE}(B, \text{ONESKERNEL}(k, k))$
- 11: $(x, y, w, h) \leftarrow \text{BOUNDINGRECT}(B)$
- 12: $I_c \leftarrow \text{CROP}(I_{\text{pre}}, x, y, w, h)$
- 13: $B_c \leftarrow \text{GRAY2RGB}(\text{CROP}(B, x, y, w, h))$
- 14: $I_{\text{crop}}^{\text{seg}} \leftarrow \text{BITWISEAND}(I_c, B_c)$
- 15: **return** $I_{\text{crop}}^{\text{seg}}, s$

World method (Algorithm 1), which assumes that the scene-averaged response approximates neutral grey:

$$\alpha_c = \frac{\mu_{\text{grey}}}{\mu_c}, \quad \mu_{\text{grey}} = \frac{\mu_R + \mu_G + \mu_B}{3} \quad (5)$$

followed by pixel-level normalisation to $[0, 1]$:

$$X_{c,h,w} \leftarrow X_{c,h,w}/255 \quad (6)$$

2) *YOLOv11 Inference and Mask Extraction*: The corrected image is fed to a YOLOv11 instance segmentation model, which resolves three objectives simultaneously: spatial localisation (bounding box), pixel-level segmentation (mask), and species classification. The predicted mask is dilated with a $k \times k$ structuring element to preserve contour information before the fish crop is extracted (Algorithm 2). The resulting segmented crop $I_{\text{crop}}^{\text{seg}}$ is forwarded to Stage 2.

3) *Training Configuration*: A total of 225 images (117 *S. aurata*, 108 *D. labrax*) were manually annotated with bounding boxes and instance masks using CVAT in an on-premises environment, avoiding upload of proprietary images to external servers. The train/validation/test split was 180/22/23. Training was conducted for 100 epochs with batch size 16, square images of 640 px, AdamW optimiser, learning rate 0.01, and early stopping patience of 100 epochs.

Fig. 3. Stage 1 pipeline: chromatic correction → YOLOv11 instance segmentation → mask dilation and crop extraction.

B. Stage 2: Multi-Label Deformity Classification

1) *Second Preprocessing Stage*: The segmented crop undergoes three sequential transformations (Algorithm 3). First, *geometric resizing* to a fixed width of 224 px preserving species-specific mean aspect ratios (224 × 68 px for *S. aurata*; 224 × 54 px for *D. labrax*), avoiding geometric distortions that could alter deformity representations. Second, *photometric harmonisation* via histogram matching against a species-specific reference image, homogenising the chromatic distribution across acquisition sessions. Third, *intensity normalisation* to [0, 1].

2) *ResNet-34 Multi-Label Classifier*: A ResNet-34 backbone pretrained on ImageNet is fine-tuned for multi-label classification using weighted binary cross-entropy:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}} = -\frac{1}{NC} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^C \left[\omega_i^+ y_i^{(n)} \log \hat{y}_i^{(n)} + \omega_i^- (1 - y_i^{(n)}) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i^{(n)}) \right] \quad (7)$$

where ω_i^+ , ω_i^- are per-class positive/negative weights derived from sample frequency, and C is the number of deformity classes. The model outputs a vector $\hat{y} \in [0, 1]^C$; deformity i is reported as present when $\hat{y}_i \geq \tau$; if no component exceeds τ , the specimen is labelled NO_DEFORME. Algorithm 4 details the full species-aware inference flow.

Fig. 4. Stage 2 pipeline: second preprocessing → ResNet-34 multi-label inference → deformity prediction and Grad-CAM++ explanation.

Algorithm 3 Classification Preprocessing Pipeline

Require: Segmented crop I , species reference I_{ref}

Ensure: Preprocessed tensor \mathbf{X}

- 1: $I_r \leftarrow \text{RESIZE}(I, \lfloor 224/3 \rfloor, 224)$
 - 2: $I_h \leftarrow \text{HISTOGRAMMATCHING}(I_r, I_{\text{ref}}, [0.7, 0.9])$
 - 3: $I_n \leftarrow \text{NORMALIZE}(I_h)$
 - 4: **return** $\text{TOTENSOR}(I_n)$
-

3) *Grad-CAM++ Explainability*: After each inference call, Algorithm 5 generates a Grad-CAM++ heat map from the

Algorithm 4 Species-Aware Deformity Classification

Require: Crop I_{in} , species s , model path M , threshold τ **Ensure:** Deformity set P , JSON report J

```
1:  $s \leftarrow \text{NORMALIZESPECIES}(s)$ 
2: if  $s \notin \{\text{DORADA}, \text{LUBINA}\}$  then
3:   raise UnknownSpeciesError
4: end if
5: Load weights  $W$ , parameters  $\Theta$ , histogram reference  $H$  for
   species  $s$ 
6:  $F \leftarrow \text{LOADCLASSIFIER}(W, \Theta)$ 
7:  $I_{\text{ref}} \leftarrow \text{READRGBIMAGE}(H)$ 
8:  $\mathbf{X} \leftarrow \text{PREPROCESS}(\text{READRGBIMAGE}(I_{in}), I_{\text{ref}})$ 
9:  $\hat{y} \leftarrow \text{INFER}(F, \mathbf{X})$ 
10:  $P \leftarrow \{C_i \mid \hat{y}_i \geq \tau\}$ 
11: if  $P = \emptyset$  then
12:    $P \leftarrow \{\text{NO\_DEFORME}\}$ 
13: end if
14:  $J \leftarrow \text{BUILDJSON}(s, P, \hat{y}, \tau)$ 
15: if Grad-CAM path is specified then
16:    $\text{RUNGRADCAM}(F, \mathbf{X}, C, \hat{y})$ 
17: end if
18: return  $P, J$ 
```

Algorithm 5 Grad-CAM++ Visualisation

Require: Classifier F_w , tensor \mathbf{X} , class list C , predictions \hat{y} , output path G **Ensure:** Heat map image

```
1:  $L \leftarrow \text{TARGETLAYER}(F_w)$ 
2:  $M \leftarrow \text{GRADCAMPLUSPLUS}(F_w, L, \mathbf{X})$ 
3:  $P \leftarrow [C_i : \hat{y}_i \geq 0.5]$ 
4: if  $P = \emptyset$  then
5:    $P \leftarrow [\text{NO\_DEFORME}]$ 
6: end if
7:  $I_d \leftarrow \text{DENORMALIZEIMAGENET}(\text{TENSORTORGB}(\mathbf{X}))$ 
8:  $V \leftarrow \text{ADDTITLE}(\text{OVERLAYCAM}(I_d, M), P)$ 
9:  $\text{SAVEIMAGE}(V, G)$ 
```

gradients of the last ResNet-34 convolutional block. The map is upsampled to input resolution and superimposed on the input image. This output does not alter the classification decision; it provides a qualitative audit trail for veterinary validation and error analysis.

C. Training Protocol and Hyperparameter Search

Classifier training used 5-fold stratified cross-validation on 90% of the data; the remaining 10% served as a permanently held-out test set, never accessed during model selection. The hyperparameter search spanned: learning rate $\{10^{-2}, 10^{-3}\}$, ResNet variant $\{18, 34, 50\}$, optimiser $\{\text{SGD}, \text{Adam}, \text{AdamW}\}$, and batch size $\{8, 16, 32\}$. The configuration with best cross-validation F1-score—identical for both species—was: **ResNet-34**, **SGD**, $\text{lr} = 0.01$, $\text{batch} = 8$. Fixed constants: maximum 200 epochs, early stopping patience 20 (zero delta), loss function (7) with $\omega_i^+ = N/(C \cdot n_i^+)$ and $\omega_i^- = N/(C \cdot n_i^-)$.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Detection and Segmentation

Table I summarises YOLOv11 performance on the 100-image test set. Both species achieve $\text{Recall} = 1.0$ (zero false

TABLE I

STAGE 1 TEST-SET PERFORMANCE. METRICS ARE IDENTICAL FOR THE BOUNDING-BOX AND MASK HEADS.

Species	Prec.	Recall	F1	mAP50-95
<i>S. aurata</i>	0.9952	1.0000	0.9976	0.9950
<i>D. labrax</i>	0.9955	1.0000	0.9978	0.9950

TABLE II

STAGE 2 GLOBAL TEST-SET PERFORMANCE (WEIGHTED MACRO AVERAGE OVER ALL DEFORMITY CLASSES PER SPECIES).

Species	Accuracy	F1	Precision	Recall
<i>S. aurata</i>	0.9742	0.8493	0.8573	0.8517
<i>D. labrax</i>	0.9421	0.7207	0.7709	0.6942

negatives) with precision above 0.995. The species confusion matrix is perfect: 100/100 sea bream and 130/130 sea bass correctly classified, with zero cross-species errors. These results, obtained with only 225 manually labelled images, reflect the visual simplicity of the task under controlled acquisition conditions (uniform background, lateral projection, single specimen per frame). Crucially, this near-perfect segmentation stage guarantees that the crops delivered to Stage 2 are of consistent quality, decoupling segmentation error from classification error.

B. Deformity Classification

Table II shows global classifier performance. The *S. aurata* model consistently outperforms *D. labrax* across all metrics ($\Delta\text{F1} = 0.129$). Accuracy is an unreliable metric in multi-label problems with class imbalance [21]—it benefits from the abundance of true negatives when most specimens present few concurrent deformities—so the reference metric is the weighted macro F1-score.

Table III breaks down per-class performance for both species. For *S. aurata*, five of seven classes exceed $\text{PR-AUC} \geq 0.91$; operculum and SBS achieve perfect precision (1.00) with $\text{ROC-AUC} > 0.998$. The lowest-performing classes are mouth ($\text{PR-AUC} = 0.776$) and snout ($\text{PR-AUC} = 0.715$), both involving anatomically adjacent cranial structures whose lateral projections can partially overlap, inducing mutual confusion. For *D. labrax*, only SBS surpasses $\text{PR-AUC} = 0.90$; vertebral fusion scores $\text{PR-AUC} = 0.683$ with $\text{Recall} = 0.57$, meaning approximately four in ten real cases are missed—an unacceptable miss rate for industrial quality control without human oversight.

Training dynamics are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. The *S. aurata* model converges smoothly before epoch 80, with a narrow cross-fold standard deviation band. The *D. labrax* model displays substantially wider inter-fold variance, consistent with its smaller corpus and severe class imbalance. Precision consistently exceeds recall during convergence for *D. labrax*, revealing a conservative bias towards false negatives over false positives.

TABLE III
PER-CLASS TEST-SET PERFORMANCE FOR BOTH SPECIES. BEST VALUES PER COLUMN WITHIN EACH SPECIES ARE IN **BOLD**.

Species	Deformity	Prec.	Recall	ROC-AUC	PR-AUC
<i>S. aurata</i>	Mouth	0.75	0.67	0.9781	0.7755
	Caudal	0.89	0.94	0.9994	0.9936
	Vert. fusion	0.86	0.88	0.9624	0.9169
	Lordosis	0.81	0.93	0.9960	0.9586
	Snout	0.69	0.87	0.9731	0.7147
	Operculum	1.00	0.93	0.9993	0.9955
	SBS	1.00	0.75	0.9983	0.9642
<i>D. labrax</i>	Vert. fusion	0.80	0.57	0.9123	0.6825
	Lordosis	0.85	0.69	0.9274	0.8282
	SBS	0.67	0.82	0.9627	0.9012

Fig. 5. Training dynamics for the *S. aurata* ResNet-34 classifier: loss, F1-score, precision, and recall over epochs. Solid lines: cross-fold mean; shaded bands: ± 1 standard deviation across folds.

Fig. 6. Training dynamics for the *D. labrax* ResNet-34 classifier. Note the wider inter-fold variance compared with *S. aurata*, reflecting the smaller corpus and stronger class imbalance.

C. Pipeline Throughput

Table IV reports P1/P50/P99 latencies per stage over 1,024 images stored on SSD. The full pipeline meets the 2 img/s requirement on both CPU (AMD Ryzen 7 9700X) (≈ 3.17 img/s)

TABLE IV
INFERENCE LATENCY (MS/IMAGE) OVER 1,024 IMAGES FROM SSD STORAGE. CPU: AMD RYZEN 7 9700X; GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 5080.

Stage	CPU			GPU		
	P1	P50	P99	P1	P50	P99
YOLOv11	77.8	83.9	169.0	10.9	11.1	13.0
ResNet-34	10.9	11.4	42.0	4.3	4.4	5.0
Full iter.	289.6	315.3	422.9	215.7	233.2	252.0

and GPU NVIDIA GeForce RTX 5080 (≈ 4.29 img/s). GPU acceleration is asymmetric: YOLOv11 benefits from a $7.57\times$ speedup (median CPU/GPU), driven by the dense convolutional and attention operations of the segmentation head. ResNet-34 yields a more modest $2.62\times$ due to its smaller parameter count and lower arithmetic intensity. Critically, the net speedup for the full iteration is only $1.35\times$, revealing that non-GPU-accelerated operations—I/O, host-to-device transfers, CPU preprocessing—are the binding bottleneck. On CPU, the P99/P50 ratios of 2.01 (YOLO) and 3.67 (ResNet-34) reflect OS scheduling jitter; these drop to ≤ 1.17 on GPU, confirming the deterministic nature of CUDA kernel execution.

D. Grad-CAM++ Visualisation

Figs. 7 and 8 show representative heat maps for both species covering four diagnostic scenarios: correct prediction with spatially coherent activation; correct prediction on a healthy specimen; morphological confusion between adjacent classes; and a false negative with uninformative map.

For vertebral fusion in *S. aurata*, activations concentrate on the posterior trunk and caudal base—the anatomically expected vertebral projection region for lateral images. Lordosis in *D. labrax* activates the mid-dorsal curvature, coherent with the characteristic concavity of this pathology. Mouth–snout confusions in *S. aurata* produce activations spread over the entire anterior cranial region, reflecting the topographic proximity of both structures and the limited spatial resolution of the last convolutional feature map. Confusions between lordosis and SBS in *D. labrax* yield overlapping dorso-caudal activations, consistent with the fact that both pathologies affect adjacent segments of the axial skeleton.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Multi-Label vs. Binary-Per-Class Formulation

The multi-label formulation avoids deploying $N_c \times N_e = 10$ independent binary classifiers (7 for *S. aurata*, 3 for *D. labrax*), each requiring separate training, validation, and maintenance cycles. More critically, extending the system to new species or deformity classes under a binary-per-class scheme demands retraining all classifiers of the affected species, compromising scalability; the multi-label model requires a single retraining step. Shared convolutional layers also enable intra-model knowledge transfer across deformity classes [22], beneficial for underrepresented classes: operculum achieves PR-AUC = 0.995 despite having fewer training samples. Finally, the documented

Fig. 7. Grad-CAM++ scenarios for *S. aurata*: (a) correct prediction; (b) false negative; (c,e) morphological confusion; (d) partial prediction; (f) healthy specimen correctly classified. *Labels*: ground truth; *Preds*: model output.

Fig. 8. Grad-CAM++ scenarios for *D. labrax*: (a) uninformative map; (b) correct prediction; (c,e) morphological confusion; (d,f) healthy specimen correctly classified.

co-occurrence of multiple deformities in the same specimen reinforces the semantic appropriateness of multi-label framing; a binary-per-class ensemble would require parallel inference over all N_c classifiers to obtain the same diagnosis, increasing total latency.

B. Conservative Bias in *D. labrax* and Remediation

The significantly lower recall (0.694) versus precision (0.771) in *D. labrax* reflects the 65.98% dominance of healthy specimens, which biases \mathcal{L}_{BCE} towards reducing false positives at the expense of false negatives. In an industrial quality-control context, missing a defective specimen carries a higher economic and sanitary cost than incorrectly rejecting a healthy one. Mitigation strategies include: (i) focal loss [23] for adaptive down-weighting of easy negatives; (ii) SMOTE-based synthetic oversampling [24] of deficit classes; (iii) systematic acquisition of additional images for underrepresented deformities, particularly vertebral fusion in *D. labrax*.

C. Computational Bottleneck and Optimisation Roadmap

The $1.35\times$ net GPU speedup, far below the $7.57\times$ achieved by YOLO alone, confirms that I/O and CPU-side preprocessing saturate the pipeline at the current throughput target. Asynchronous image prefetch during GPU inference, INT8 quantisation via quantisation-aware training followed by TensorRT export, and ONNX + OpenVINO compilation for deployments without discrete GPU represent a clear optimisation roadmap. INT8 quantisation alone typically yields a $2\text{--}4\times$ latency reduction with minimal accuracy degradation for classification networks trained with quantisation awareness—a high-priority future work item.

D. Limitations

Three methodological limitations must be acknowledged. *First*, test sets for rare classes in *D. labrax* are too small to report confidence intervals on PR-AUC; future evaluations should adopt bootstrapping protocols [25] to quantify statistical uncertainty. *Second*, all latency measurements used SSD-resident images; network-attached storage (including the MinIO backend of the ALEVIA data space) may add tens to hundreds of milliseconds per image, potentially violating the 2 img/s requirement at narrow bandwidths. *Third*, the entire evaluation was conducted under controlled laboratory conditions; performance degradation due to production-site variability (camera calibration drift, ageing illumination, fish handling stress) has not been characterised and constitutes a prerequisite for regulatory certification.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented and evaluated ALEVIA, a two-stage deep learning pipeline for automatic morphological deformity detection in juvenile *Sparus aurata* and *Dicentrarchus labrax*. Stage 1 achieves near-perfect instance segmentation ($mAP_{50-95} = 0.995$, $Recall = 1.0$ on both species) with only 225 manually annotated images. Stage 2 reaches weighted macro F1-scores of 0.849 and 0.721 for the two species on independently held-out test sets, with throughput exceeding the 2 img/s deployment requirement on commodity CPU hardware. Grad-CAM++ maps confirm anatomically coherent attention patterns across the range of diagnosed deformities, providing an interpretable audit trail that supports acceptance by veterinary experts.

The system currently stands at Technology Readiness Level 4 (laboratory-validated). The primary barriers to TRL 5–6 are: (i) augmentation of the training corpus for deficit classes (mouth, snout, and vertebral fusion in *D. labrax*); (ii) correction of the conservative recall bias in *D. labrax* via focal loss or targeted oversampling; (iii) prospective validation on data captured at unseen production facilities. The ALEVIA Gaia-X-compliant federated data space provides the infrastructure for systematic, privacy-preserving cross-facility corpus accumulation—offering a long-term path towards TRL 7–8 and continuous, data-sovereign model improvement across the Mediterranean aquaculture sector.

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